

Emerging Trends in English Literature: An Analytical Study

Deepankar Jaluthariya

Assistant professor (English), Govt. PG College Thanagazi Alwar (Rajasthan)

*Corresponding Author Email id: d2jaluthariya@gmail.com

Received: 22/07/2023; Accepted 05/08/2023; Published 25/10/2023

ABSTRACT

As we know that literature is the mirror of society and a productive work of art. With the change of the time, the form of literature is also changing the main goal of this paper is to explain and illustrate how social media, E-books, digital media and other means of social networking have changed the literary scenario in modern times. English literature is being changed by giving it a new direction and condition through electronic technology and other tools of social networking like tweeter, facebook, instagram, and whatsapp. Today the lifestyle of man has changed so much that he does not have enough time to sit and study literary works of art. Books, news-papers and magazines seem to be losing their significance in this electronic age. Due to cybernetic reading the practices of liner, closed and solitary reading is ending. Through social media any literary work of art becomes available to read and analyse immediately on computer screen with the single click of mouse on various blogs. Humans engage themselves in deep and meaningful discussion on various social, religious, political and literary issues. Social media is a great platform to discuss and exchange ideas on any issue. According to some thinkers art and literature are developing due to social media but due to modern technology the quality of literary works is also decreasing. Now a days the trend of 6 word novel, hypertext, flash fiction and micro fiction is going on in English literature. This study reveals that there has been a massive revolution in the field of English literature which is the direct result of globalization and westernization.

Key words: Digital media, electronic technology, cybernetic reading, hypertext, flash fiction, globalization.

In modern times, Emerging trends in the field of English literature such as social media, digital media, blogging and the other means of social networking have had wide impact on English literature. English literature is considered as a productive skill. It is believed that due to widespread influence of social media books, newspapers, articles and magazines have lost their significance. Man has accepted the tools of digital media as the only mean of gaining more and more knowledge. He can access the desired information on digital screen with the single click of mouse from high-speed internet connected devices. Today the text reading culture is almost dying due to the influence of social media.

The present generation does not like to read long paragraphs and novels in detailed form. For example, the long descriptions of wessex landscape in Thomas hardy`s novels do not appeal today`s reader. Due to cybernetic reading beauty of wessex has lost it`s importance to the present day reader.it is no wonder that the internet has made the world smaller to exchange their ideas. English literature is such a door through which new ideas are exchanged. The form of literature has changed a lot in present time. Recent trends of novel such as flash fiction, micro fiction, tweeter fiction, blogging and micro blogging are being introduced in the field of fiction writing. These type of writers uses least number of words. O` Henry, Ernest Hemingway and Anton Chekov are known as flash fiction writers. Flash fiction is short, catchy and flashy. Two decades ago people used to sit in library to read novels, articles, magazines and research papers to find the answer of their project. But now a days no one likes to go to the library for reading and find their solutions. He can access everything within few seconds on google without wasting his time.

In earlier times every reader of English literature had oxford dictionary which was considered as the bible of English. But today people do not need English dictionary. He searches everything on word web. The present day reader of English literature downloads various types of English dictionary applications in his smart phone and can access the meaning of the words immediately. Today instead of reading books, magazines, newspapers, articles and research papers, the traditional means of study, he started reading English literature through smart phones, tablets and personal computers. Cybernetic reading replaced the traditional mode of linear, closed and solitary reading in this electronic age. Social media, e-books, blogging ,tweetering, face book whats app, instagram and other means of digital media have changed the literary scenario. E- book technology is a convenient mean of digital media to access even the historical writers. Charles dickens and William Shakespeare have their tweeter account which play an eminent role in generating reader`s interest in English literature. A reader of English literature can read William Shakespeare, John keats`,William wordsworth, Charles dickens and Thomas hardy through digital media. Swipespeare app is available to read William Shakespeare for English literature students, scholars and professionals and keep alive the ancient writers and their works. This type of application help to enable knowledge transfer within modern society as it provides individual with an opportunity to reflect on production of previous knowledge.

There has been a trend of six word novel in the field of English literature. Marcy`s –one gun, two shots and three dead and Rebecca james` after she died, he came alive are the finest examples of six word novel. A long, detailed and descriptive novel is easy to write whereas writing and reading six word novel requires a lot of creativity on the part of writer as well as reader. In earlier times no one had ever thought about the trend of six word novel in English literature would attract the attention of the readers of English literature in near future. Blogging pages provide platform to the new budding writers to expose their talent to the world and become famous instantly.

A blog is a forum on internet where Its members exchange their views and share their experiences on vaious pages. Blogging, micro blogging, tweetering are currently in vogue as cutting edge trends in moden times. According to a study by tuft university, a person spends 22% of his time per day in viewing blogs and pages on internet. Noor and John believe that social media enhances the connection between writer and reader. Digital media is commercial and cosumer based technology in which information is presented in distorting way. Due to electronic revolution reading has become easier.

But literary classicists are dissatisfied with the recent techniques introduced in English literature. According to them recent trends in English literature are devaluing the tradition of classical literature and are promoting grammatical errors, superficialities, disregard to refrences, misspellings and slang words in English literature. Two decades ago, the habit of diary writing was excellent way to preserve memories but due to the impact of digital media the practice of diary writing is almost finished now. People upload their album, scrapbook, photos on facebook, instagram and twitter. These are the safest modes to preserve their memories. As long as the account remains memories will be in that account and the comments of friends will also be added.

New digital trends are being introduced in indian education system such as google classroom, zoom, google meet, webex, online chat session and interactive language labs. These emerging trends are result of communication revolution. Young generation prefers to acquire knowledge through digital means of technology. Recently Non textual culture has flourished through digital media. In each era, new styles of literature have developed. In earlier times the emphasis was laid on author and his history. Before covid 19 face to face interaction was the unique mode of communication. But during the period of covid 19 online methods of teaching and learning were adopted.

English literature follows the rules of art rather than the rules of nature. Effective literature is the one in which stable, clear, convenient and coherent motives resonate between the reader and writer. If it is not so, then such literature is worthless which can be compared to a conversation with a stranger with whom the stable, clear, coherent and convenient communication do not resonate. In modern times, English literature can be accessed on digital platforms in a quick manner. It allows easy access to vital information and exchanging ideas allowing literature to be analyzed.

But despite all these shortcomings, it can be said that recent trends have given birth to the new forms of English literature. Social media platform presents literature in the form of stories which is read by innumerable people on digital platform. The recent trends also allows the amalgamation of cultures between societies. The contradiction occurs because of the difference between the written literature and the literature available on social

media. Literature available on social media is inaccurate, unauthentic, illogical and disqualitative. Information available in books, magazines, articles is accurate, authentic and logical and full of quality. Apart from the literature available on social media, the reader needs to have an extra knowledge of books for complete and true analysis of literature. There must be a strong connection between the reader and writer. Lack of strong bond between them leads to worthless, meaningless and fruitless literary analysis. But despite the pros and cons it is difficult to dismiss that the internet culture is breaking the boundaries with regards to literature. The multiple ways of sharing literary works such as facebook, tweeter, instagram, e-books booktube, book twitter, email and viber allows writer and reader to exchange their ideas and engage them in deep and meaningful conversation and allowing two way conversation in comparison to one way monologue.

REFERENCES

- [1]. Dr. P. Pandia Rajammal: Emerging trends in English literature
- [2]. Ercan Gurova: How recent trends shape English literature
- [3]. Adrian: trends in English language teaching today under hill, “trends in English language teaching today, M ED Magazine issue 18,2007
- [4]. Yogesh Ramani: Trends in English language teaching today
- [5]. Goodwyn, Andrew. English in the Digital Age: Information and Communications Technology and the teaching of English. London: Cassell, 1999. Print.
- [6]. Lamy, Marie-noelle, and katerina zourou. Social Networking for language education. 2013. Print.
- [7]. Lomborg stine. Social media, social genres: Making Sense of the Ordinary. 2013. Print.
- [8]. Marcus, Laura, and Peter Nicholls. The Cambridge History of twentieth-Century English Literature. Cambridge, UK: Cambridge University Press, 2004. Print.
- [9]. Morris, Tee, and Phillppa Ballantine. Social Media for Writers: Marketing Strategies for Building Your Audience and Selling Books. 2015. Print.
- [10]. Noor, Al-Deen H. S, and John A. Hendricks. Social Media: Usage and impact. Lanham, Md: Lexington Books, 2012. Print.
- [11]. Poplawski, Paul. English Literature in Context. Cambridge University Press, 2008. Print.
- [12]. Tharakan, Tony. Writing a Novel? Just Tweet it. Reuters.com India Insight. 2009. 21 January 2016. <<http://blogs.reuters.com/2009/08/09/writing-a-novel-just-tweet-it/>>
- [13]. Tufts University. Social Media Overview. Tufts University. 2016. 21 January 2016. <<http://webcomm.tufts.edu/social-media-overview13/>>
- [14]. Sunita Sinha, 20th Century Literature: Emerging Trends, 2014.Print.
- [15]. The New Encyclopedia Britannica, Vol. London: William Benton Publishers. 1926.Print.